

What Counts as Success in the Assessment of Mathematics?

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Few topics generate such heated debate in education as assessment. Academics, policy makers, parents, employers, students and the general public all have views on assessment, be it low and high stakes, summative, formative, peer and or self assessment or whether it is authentic, dynamic, diagnostic, strengths based, ecological, inclusive, feeding back and forward or on teachers' assessment literacy (Black & William, 2018; Elder, Rood and Damiani, 2018; Douglas et al., 2012; Lauchlan & Jones Daly, 2023). Looney et al. (2018) talk of teacher assessment identity; there is also the power differential between the assessor and assessed (Imperio & Seitz, 2023), the backwash effect on pedagogy (Alderson and Wall, 1993), valuing what can be measured more than measuring what we value (Biesta, 2014), computer based assessment (Martin & Lazendic, 2018), test development (Downing & Haladyna, 2006), the use and abuse of standardised assessment (Penn, 2023), value added models (Marks, 2021), the influence of AI on assessment (Swiecki et al. 2022), international comparative assessment, opposition to what is called Baby PISA (OECD, 2015; Urban & Swadener, 2016) and of course the controversy in Ireland around teachers assessing their own students in State examinations (Molloy, 2022). This is before we get to validity and reliability and the purposes of assessment.

Instigating change in the area of assessment can be fraught with political and ideological aspects far removed from the evidence. Here we have an opportunity to listen and engage with four very different but complementary papers which assess the evidence as they pertain to assessment for success in mathematics.

Therese Dooley focuses on the key area of formative assessment and how it can be effectively used in the teaching of mathematics. She presents the findings from a recent review and outlines the complexity of measuring impact with different definitions and foci. The review points to initial very promising results with some more modest findings in recent research. She points to the potential of learning trajectories and how they can benefit formative assessment in combination with other pedagogical strategies. Dooley highlights the design and use of revelatory tasks as a window into student thinking and knowledge when combined with close observation, interviewing, examination of work samples, diagrams, concepts maps and reflections on learning as beneficial ways of utilising formative assessment in mathematics.

However, the review highlights self assessment as having the greatest impact on achievement followed by peer assessment, with both having greater effect than teacher directed assessment. Such assessment involves reflection on the quality of work and the extent to which goals were achieved and is linked to metacognition and self-regulated learning. Linking with Zita Lysaght's paper, the complexity of practice for the teacher is highlighted involving making decisions about feedback, understanding learning trajectories and misconceptions and how to respond to these effectively. It also entails a mindset change in developing a learning environment that is shared with students and a mitigation of the

power differential in allowing students more autonomy in assessment as part of the learning process. A key question which arises here is how this is best done in the context of teacher professional learning?

Zita Lysaght focuses on the interaction between assessment for learning and the development of short term learning progressions in primary mathematics by pre-service teachers. She highlights the challenge for students of assessing where the learners are at in designing appropriate goals and how this links to their knowledge of learning trajectories in mathematics. Somewhat controversially she links student difficulties in executing this task to the criteria for entry to the B.Ed in Ireland in relation to attainment in post primary mathematics, arguing that the low expectations are a “hostage to fortune”.

There is no denying the levels of knowledge and skills involved in accurately assessing current student performance and using learning trajectory knowledge to craft next steps in learning and bridge the gap. A key question which arises here is in relation to what is reasonable to expect at initial teacher education level and what additional expectations should reside in the area of further teacher professional learning linking with Dooley? A related question is how best formative assessment is learned- what is the optimum balance between discrete, embedded and applied placement approaches?

Gerry Shiel explores new directions in summative assessment and highlights the affordances offered by technology in the area. Opportunities for interim assessment blocks and greater data based decision making are possible. He also highlights the use of adaptive testing which builds differentiation into the tasks. This is an element that does not feature yet in Irish assessment. He sees a greater merging of formative and summative assessment with greater use of summative assessment for diagnostic purposes. Politically, different systems have attached greater importance to the results of summative assessments and used the results in suspect ways for teacher and school evaluation. Other uses include their incorporation in value added models, measuring progress over time and controlling for socio-economic contexts. Systems also grapple with reporting mechanisms to parents and what approach best relays key contextualised information taking limitations into account. A key question here is how Ireland can strike a balance between using the benign features of summative assessment while avoiding the misuse of data for other purposes.

Vasiliki Pitsia traces Ireland’s involvement with international large scale assessment of mathematics achievement. From the late 1980s Ireland began to regularly participate in international assessment of mathematics including the OECD’s Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the IEA’s Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TiMSS). PISA targets 15 year old students and TIMSS the equivalent of fourth class primary and second year post primary. She outlines the content areas, cognitive processes and application contexts for the assessments. Across both assessments Irish students have performed well with one exception. In addition lower-achieving students have also done relatively well but there are concerns about the lower than expected performance of higher achieving students. The one exception of PISA 2009 does present a salutary tale of the extent of the reach of influence of the results on policy in Ireland. While it subsequently has been shown to have been an over reaction with plausible explanations offered for the low

performance in 2009, the impact on the teaching of mathematics has been significant from curricula reform, mandatory standardised testing in primary schools, a new numeracy strategy which impacted practice at primary level and the extension of teacher education programmes forming part of the strategy. A key question here is the extent to which such assessments should influence policy and practice and the process through which those decisions are made? Valisilki argues that current practice has much to learn from the assessments in moving away from state examination driven pedagogy to developing mathematical knowledge and skills more aligned with the intentions of PISA and TIMSS.

The papers present us with challenges for the future at classroom, initial teacher education, national and international levels across formative and summative assessment which impact hugely on success in mathematics.

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